

SensApp

D5.2 Report on sensitivity and specificity for tau protein

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Author(s)	Martina Mugnano
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1. Introduction

The reaction steps after spotting the glass slides by DSS have been performed fully manually in CNR labs, due to the lack of liquid handling automation from Ginolis. This required time-consuming implementation of the reaction steps in CNR labs, especially crucial for the challenging samples at low protein concentration. In fact, even little variations in handling the reagents and the slides produce variations in background levels and non-specific signals that can be highly detrimental especially at low concentrations. Therefore, the experimental activities for characterizing the limit of detection and for building the calibration lines in pure protein samples took longer than expected and only the last two months of the project (M41 and M42) were focused on the experiments with body fluids.

The functionalized slides undergo degradation of the reactive surface through contact with air and humidity, and therefore they must be used as soon as possible after opening the package. Also in this case, this is particularly detrimental when working with challenging samples at high dilutions. In fact, the lack of automated reaction steps prevented us from using more than 2 slides per day, thus facing the additional issue of reactivity degradation over days. Concerning the experiments in body fluids, we followed the suggestions from the reviewers in the second-year review meeting by focusing the attention on body fluids poorer in proteins than plasma, such as urine and saliva, also considering the limited time available. In addition, the results on alternative fluids to plasma and serum can launch the DSS towards applications with other kinds of biomarker targets.

The dissemination level of this Deliverable D5.2 is public. We achieved various results in this workpackage which are currently under consideration for exploitation in patents and scientific publications. Therefore, according to the Art.27 of the GA, we are obliged to protect such results before their exploitation and the sensitive data (e.g. experimental details; graphs; etc.) are not presented in this deliverable D5.2.

2. Samples

This Deliverable deals with the tests on the biomarker Tau. We bought it from RayBiotech (code 228-10236) for performing the calibration tests. The solution was resuspended in distilled H₂O and serial dilutions were prepared starting from 100 µg/mL down to 0.16 pg/mL. Solutions of Tau protein in distilled water at fixed concentrations of 50 µg/mL and 4 pg/mL were analyzed by DLS and LDME. Hydrodynamic diameter (dHD) values and ζ potentials were measured using a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instruments) instrument at a scattering angle of 173°. The measurements were performed in triplicate at 25 °C for water-based samples. The average dHD in case of 4 pg/ml was about 71.4 nm, whereas it was 11.1 nm at 50 µg/mL. The Z-potential analysis shows a net negative charge for both concentrations, thus leading us to choose functionalized glass slides with amine groups on the surface bringing a positive net charge. The deposited target molecules are therefore immobilized on the surface via an electrostatic adsorption. The typical dissociation energy for this kind of electrostatic bond is 130 kJ/mol. We used commercial amine glass slides from PolyAn (Berlin), usually employed for microarray applications, and the figure below shows the schematic view of these PolyAn amine surface.

Amine Surfaces

for non-covalent coupling of negatively charged biochemical species
via electrostatical adsorption

It is important to note that the slides come in bags filled with inert gas and they undergo degradation if in contact with air, therefore they have to be used as soon as possible after bag aperture to have a reasonable reproducibility. This is especially crucial when working at low protein concentration where the binding efficiency on the slide is of fundamental importance.

Other functionalized slides were tested such as epoxy surfaces to promote a covalent coupling of N-terminal biochemical species. Epoxides are cyclic ethers with a highly strained three-member ring. Epoxy rings can be easily reacted with nucleophiles e.g. amines, hydrazines, thiols, hydroxides and carboxyl groups. Compared to NHS esters or 1,4-Phenylene isothiocyanates (PDITC) the epoxy surface is more stable and has a longer shelf-life. Epoxy surfaces are stable up to temperatures of 40° C and are also more stable against humidity compared to NHS and PDITC-surfaces. The nucleophilic addition is catalysed by acid or basic conditions. Under acidic conditions, the oxygen in the ring is positively charged, which facilitates the nucleophilic attack. Under basic conditions the least substituted carbon is attacked by the applied nucleophile in a standard SN2 reaction. For activation of epoxy surfaces a pre-treatment with triethylamine was carried out for 10 minutes at room temperature. We do not report here the results obtained with epoxy slides due to poor repeatability. Further studies are needed to standardize the pre-treatment of the slides able to promote the covalent binding.

The tests in body fluids were first carried out in solutions of plasma-like fluids made of fetal bovine serum at 5% and 10% in distilled water. The first one clogged the pin after 10-15 min jetting, while the second one after about 1-2 min, thus preventing the realization of reproducible spots on the target slide. Therefore, considering the limited time available and the suggestion from the monitor experts in the second review meeting to test body fluids alternative to plasma, we did not proceed with human plasma samples and we believe that additional efforts are required in a future project to pre-treat and even to dilute plasma samples to avoid pin clogging. We tested the behaviour of the DSS technology on commercial artificial urine and saliva fluids, usually employed just for testing new biosensors. Both solutions were bought from Biochemizone. The figure below reports the composition of these commercial fluids.

Major Composition: (Y/N) Y	Major Components: (Y/N) Y
CAS: 7447-40-7 Potassium Chloride	Ammonium Chloride
CAS: 7778-77-0 Potassium Phosphate	Calcium chloride dihydrate
CAS: 7647-14-5 Sodium Chloride	Magnesium Sulphate
CAS: 10035-04-8 Calcium Chloride Dihydrate	Potassium Chloride
CAS: 791-18-6 Magnesium Chloride	Sodium Chloride
CAS: 9004-32-4 Carboxymethyl cellulose sodium	Sodium Phosphate, dibasic
CAS: 7558-79-4 Sodium Phosphate, dibasic	Sodium Citrate
CAS: 99-76-3 methyl 4-hydroxybenzoate	Sodium sulfate decahydrate
CAS: 7732-18-5 Water, distilled Water, deionized Water	Sodium phosphate monobasic monohydrate
Enzyme: Amylase, Lysozyme (customizable)	Optional: Urea, Creatinine hydrochloride, Sodium Sulphite: (Y/N) Y
Stabilizer: Y (customizable)	
Viscosity Enhancer: Mucin: Y (customizable)	

Composition of the commercial (left) artificial saliva and (right) urine from Biochemizone.

3. Calibration tests

The solution of Tau protein in distilled water was deposited by DSS on the amine slide and afterwards the slide was incubated in a humid chamber for 2 h at 25 °C. For saturating excess protein-binding sites, the slide was covered with 2 mL of blocking solution for 1 h at 25 °C. The blocking solution was used to dilute the antibody solutions. Then the slide was washed by placing it in a Petri dish with 10 mL of PBS 1X (Gibco 10010023) for 2 min. This washing cycle (WC) was repeated three times. A solution of primary antibody, 2 mL of rabbit anti- β -Amyloid 1-42 (CellSignaling Technologies Tau D1M9X XP Rabbit mAb) at the dilution of 1:600 was deposited on the slide and incubated overnight at 4 °C. The three WCs were repeated. Finally, the secondary antibody solution (Thermo Fisher Scientific anti-Rabbit I A32733), at a concentration of 0.5 μ g/mL, was incubated 1 h at 25°C and the three WCs were repeated. The procedure was repeated for Tau samples at concentrations of 0.16 pg/mL, 50 ng/mL, 500 ng/mL and 5 μ g/mL. A linear response of the resulting fluorescence signal was obtained in the full range of concentrations.

The behaviour of artificial saliva and urine in producing spots by DSS was first tested without protein mixing and the results have been already described in D5.1 with saliva exhibiting high evaporation point and unsatisfactory droplet accumulation. Conversely, the artificial urine exhibits a satisfactory droplet

accumulation with DSS able to detect the fluorescent secondary antibody at 0.8 pg/mL in artificial urine. Due to the limited time available and the lack of an automated system for the protocol steps, the analogous immunoreaction protocol performed for A β 1-42 in artificial urine was not possible with Tau protein and additional studies are expected in a future research project.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the DSS module was able to detect the biomarker Tau protein with a LOD of 0.16 pg/mL and a linear behaviour in the range 0.16 – 5 μ g/mL in case of pure reference samples diluted in distilled water. Moreover, the comparative study performed with a commercial piezo-based biospotter (see D4.2) represents a benchmarking exercise which demonstrates the ability of DSS technology to concentrate biomolecules in tiny droplets in a reliable manner. These results open the route for developing the DSS also for applications in the field of microarray spotting.

The experiments on body fluids were performed in a short period of a couple of months and they include the experiments with artificial saliva and urine alone, to test their ability to accumulate tiny droplets by DSS, with the labelled secondary antibody (Ab2) diluted in artificial urine and saliva and with the target A β 1-42 diluted in artificial saliva and urine detected by immunoreaction protocol. The results (not reported here for confidentiality reasons) demonstrate the ability of DSS to detect Ab2 proteins at 0.8 pg/mL and A β 1-42 at 40 μ g/mL both in artificial urine which appears, at the moment, the most suitable body fluid for the DSS technology. Anyway, the DSS module requires in future the integration with an appropriate automated system for controlling the protocol steps in order to reduce the background signal from non-specific binding especially crucial when handling samples at low concentrations. Moreover, additional studies are required for pre-treating the urine samples to reduce the impact of salt-like precipitation during spot formation and alternative protocol procedures should be tested in a future project, such as labelled primary antibody and sandwich-like configurations with glass slides functionalized with a primary antibody.